

Naringenin-4'-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside : A Novel Flavanone Glycoside from the Stem of *Crotalaria striata* D.C.

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Crotalaria striata D.C.¹ is an erect herbaceous shrub, found all over India, Ceylon and Malaysia. The medicinal importance of this plant prompted us to investigate it further phytochemically. The present paper deals with the isolation of a novel flavanone glycoside, naringenin-4'-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside, from the methanol-soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract obtained from the stem of *C. striata*.

Results and Discussion

The plant material, procured from United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta, was identified at the Department of Botany of this University. The methanolic extract of the stem of the *C. striata* on CC over silica gel (B.D.H.) gave a pale yellow solid, which was identified as a 5,7,4'-trisubstituted flavanone glycoside with free hydroxyl groups at 5 and 7 positions.

Acid hydrolysis of 1 with 7% ethanolic H₂SO₄, gave equimolar quantity of aglycone (2) and L-rhamnose as sugar moiety (pc and glc). The aglycone showed bathochromic shifts of 54 nm in band-I and 14 nm in band-II with NaOMe relative to MeOH (absent in glycoside), suggesting that C-4' must be involved in glycosylation². The aglycone was identified as naringenin (spectral and chromatographic comparison)³.

The glycoside 1 yielded a pentaacetate derivative. Its ¹H nmr signal at δ 5.68–5.59 corresponds to C-2 proton. The signals at δ 3.05 and 2.60 are ascribed to C-3 axial and C-3 equatorial protons respectively. Two *meta*-coupled doublets at δ 6.82 and 7.28 correspond to C-6 and C-8 protons of ring-A. Two *ortho*-coupled doublets at δ 7.25 and 6.72 are attributed to A₂B₂ pattern of B-ring. The details of spectral data are presented in Experimental.

Permethylation⁴ of 1 followed by acid hydrolysis gave a partial methyl ether, which was characterised as 5,7-di-O-methylnaringenin by direct comparison with authentic sample (co-chromatography, m.p., m.m.p.)⁵. The methyl-

lated sugar obtained was characterised as 2,3,4-tri-O-methylrhamnose by tlc⁶. This establishes⁵ that L-rhamnose is linked to C-4' of aglycone. Compound 1 on treatment with NaIO₄ consumed 2.01 mol of periodate and liberated 1.07 mol of formic acid indicating the presence of one molecule of L-rhamnose attached to the glycoside and also showed the presence of the sugar in pyranose form⁷. Enzymatic hydrolysis of the glycoside⁸ with takadiastase solution suggests α -linkage between the aglycone and L-rhamnose.

On the basis of the above findings, compound 1 has been identified as naringenin-4'-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Reichert microscope hot-stage apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a JEOL-GX (270 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ¹³C nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a FT instrument (50 MHz).

Air-dried and powdered stem (3 kg) of the plant was extracted with 95% ethanol and the extract concentrated under reduced pressure to give a dark-brown coloured viscous mass. It was then successively extracted with petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol.

The concentrated methanolic fraction on tlc using EtOAc-MeOH-H₂O (10 : 7 : 3) and I₂-vapour as visualising agent gave a single spot. It was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel for further purification. The fraction eluted with EtOAc-MeOH (7 : 3) afforded a pale yellow solid (1) which on crystallisation from methanol gave pale yellow crystals (1), m.p. 205–06°, [M⁺] 418 (Found : C, 60.23; H, 5.24. C₂₁H₂₂O₉ calcd. for : C, 60.28; H, 5.26%); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 286, 326 sh, 355 (+NaOMe) 300, 330 sh, 380, (+AlCl₃) 309, 336 sh, 386, (+AlCl₃ + HCl) 309, 375, (+NaOAc) 298, 320 sh, 332 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 2910, 1640 (C=O), 1500, 1205, 1110–1000 (glycosidic), 1150, 800 cm⁻¹; positive tests for flavanone glycoside⁹.

Acetylation of 1 : Compound 1 on acetylation with Ac₂O/Py (1 : 2) for 48 h at room temperature and on usual work-up afforded a pentaacetate derivative, C₃₁H₃₂O₁₄, m.p. 175–76°; ¹H nmr (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 5.68–5.59 (1H, dd, J 11.5 Hz and 3.5 Hz, H-2), 3.05 (1H, dd, J 17 Hz and

1; R = α -L-Rhamnopyranoside
2; R = H

4 Hz, H-3ax), 2.60 (1H, dd, J 17 and 4 Hz, H-3 eq), 6.82 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.28 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 2.45 (3H, s, OAc-5), 2.40 (3H, s, OAc-7), 7.25 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.72 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-3', 5'), 5.44 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-1' of rhamnose), 5.22–4.66 (4H, m, rhamnosyl-H), 0.79 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, rhamnosyl methyl), 2.01–2.19 (9H, m, sugar acetoxy); m/z 628 $[M]^+$, 356 $[M^+$ - acetylated sugar moiety] $^{+}$; 272 $[356-2Ac]^+$, or $[aglycone\ fragment]^{+}$, 273 $[rhamn\ (Ac)_3]^+$, 153 $[A_1 + H^+]^{+}$, 94 $[B_2]^{+}$, 120 $[B_3]^{+}$, 179 $[aglycone\ fragment^+ - (B-ring)']^{+}$.

Acid hydrolysis of 1: A solution of the glycoside (1) in 7% H_2SO_4 was heated on water-bath for 2 h at 100°. The separated aglycone was washed with water, dried and crystallised from methanol as yellow needles of naringenin, m.p. 248–50°, $[M]^+$ 272 (Found : C, 66.19; H, 4.45. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ calcd. for : C, 66.17; H, 4.41%); λ_{max} (MeOH) 287, 328, (+NaOMe) 245, 323 sh, 330, (+ $AlCl_3$) 300, 312 sh, 375, (+ NaOAc) 284 sh, 323, (+NaOAc + H_3BO_3) 289, 332 sh, 340 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 430, 2 945, 1 680, 1 645, 1 200, 1 012, 820 cm^{-1} .

The aqueous hydrolysate after neutralisation with $BaCO_3$ and $BaSO_4$ was filtered. The filtrate was subjected to paper chromatography using n-butanol-acetic acid-water (60 : 28.5 : 16.5 and 4 : 1 : 5) with authentic sugar as checks, and aniline hydrogen phthalate and *p*-anisidine phosphate solutions as spray reagents. The R_f values of sugar were identical with those of rhamnose (0.37, 0.28).

Glc of sugars: The neutral hydrolysate was evaporated to dryness and dissolved in pyridine (5 ml), dimethylchlorosilazane (1 ml) and hexamethyldisilazane (1 ml). The mixture was separated on a column of 2% OV-1 silinised chromosorb W at 185° using N_2 flow rate of 50 ml min^{-1} . The R_t (min) values observed for the TMS ether derivatives investigated corresponded to α - and β -rhamnose (3.9, 3.8). The observed R_t values were in agreement with those

of rhamnose.

Permethylation of 1 followed by acid hydrolysis: Compound 1 (50 mg) was treated with MeI (1 ml) and Ag_2O (30 mg) in DMF (3 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred in dark at room temperature for 48 h, then filtered and the residue washed with DMF. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml). The alcohol was recovered and the syrupy residue hydrolysed with 7% H_2SO_4 . On usual work-up gave naringenin-5, 7-dimethyl ether⁵ (14 mg), m.p. 122–24° (Found : C, 68.07; H, 5.30. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ calcd. for : C, 68.00; H, 5.33%). The methylated sugar was identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, $[\alpha]_D + 26^\circ$ (in H_2O).

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